

Study the Lip Prints as an Identification Tool for Human Identification**Dharmendra Kumar¹, Smriti Sinha², Ritu³, Pankaj Kumar⁴**¹Tutor, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar²Tutor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar³Assistant Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar⁴Associate Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar

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Abstract:**Background:** "Cheiloscopy" is a technique that deals with lip prints. The pattern of fine creases on the lips is unique to the individual. They are similar to finger prints and useful in crime investigation. Aims of this study to study the uniqueness, prevalence, and gender significance of lip print patterns in human subjects.**Methods:** The study was conducted on 100 randomly selected male and female. The lip print of each subject was obtained and its pattern was analyzed according to Suzuki and Tsuchihashi classification.**Results:** The study showed that Type I lip pattern was the commonest.**Conclusion:** Our study has added to confirmation of the distinctiveness of cheiloscopy, which can be used as an additional tool for identification. Studies on lip prints being very scanty, our findings add significantly to the meagre literature on this subject. Further in-depth studies to establish prevalence of patterns in lip prints will certainly help as useful evidence in forensic investigations.**Keywords:** Lip Prints, Cheiloscopy, Identification, Forensic Dentistry, Unique.

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Introduction

The labial mucosa forms a characteristic pattern of skin creases/grooves called lip prints". Study of lip prints is called Cheiloscopy. The applications of Lip prints are similar to those of fingerprints. As they are unique we can use lip prints for identification of suspects. [1] In past there were different modalities used for identification like fingerprints, MN blood group system, and DNA finger printing: of these, finger printing is most widely used. As knowledge of using fingerprints for identification is increasing in the general population, offenders are taking care not to leave behind fingerprints at a crime scene.

So cheiloscopy can also be used as an additional tool for crime investigation. [2] One of the earliest workers in this field was "Dr. Martinez Santos from Brazil who classified the furrows on the lips and showed that they can be used for identification". [3] In the past several studies were conducted in various specialties in different parts of the world such as Czechoslovakia, Germany, Italy, France, Great Britain and Iran. [4] In the last decade, lip print studies attracted attention as a new tool for human identification. Cheiloscopy was first described by Fischer in 1902. [4] Locard

recommended usefulness of lip prints in criminal investigation and personal identification). [5] The present study had adopted Tsuchihashi classification to categorize lip prints. According to Tsuchihashi there are 6 types of lip prints. These are:

- Type I - A clear-cut groove running vertically across the lip
- Type I' - Partial-length groove of Type I
- Type II - A branched groove
- Type III - An intersected groove
- Type IV - A reticular pattern
- Type V - Other patterns [6]

Material and Methods

This is a Cross sectional study was conducted at Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar from November 2016 to March 2018. Subjects were recruited after taking written informed consent from them. A total of 100 subjects of both sex (50 from each gender) aged between 17-19 years were recruited in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Young adults without any disease related to lips, with normal lip mucosa were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Subjects having any gross congenital deformities of lips (e.g. cleft lip), and those with any inflammation, allergic to the lip stick, and with any kind of disease were excluded from our study.

All the participants were informed about the study, its method and objectives were explained in clear detail, and they were made comfortable. The lips were cleaned and a thin layer of dark red Colored lip-stick was applied on the lips, and they were asked to spread it evenly. "Hinged" portion of folded bond paper was placed between the lips and

they were instructed to press their lips by applying pressure evenly. It was then "unfolded" and the lip was divided into four quadrants by employing the dental formula generally used. The lip prints in all the quadrants were studied by us using a magnifying lens and double check was done before the data entry. Lip prints were classified by using Suzuki and Tsuchihashi classification.

The difference between males and females for lip patterns was done by Chi square test. The p value less than 0.05 were considered significant. There was no significant difference observed between genders.

Results

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of lip prints

Type	Female	Male
Type 1	22 (44%)	33 (66%)
Type 2	22 (44%)	10 (20%)
Type 3	1 (2%)	0
Type 4	4 (8%)	3 (6%)
Type 5	1 (2%)	4 (8%)

The data shows percentage wise distribution of different lip patterns

In the present study the analysis of lip print patterns revealed that no two lip prints were similar, thus establishing the uniqueness of lip prints. The commonest pattern found in our study was Type I (55%). This was followed, in order, by Type II (32%), Type IV (7%), Type V (5%) and Type III

(1%). There was a difference in gender wise distribution of lip prints.

Among females, Type I and II (44%, each (22) appear to be equally dominant patterns followed by the Type IV(8%), Type III (2%)and Type V(2%) patterns while in males, Type I (66%) was the predominant pattern followed by Type II (20%), Type V (8%), Type IV (6%), and Type III (0%) patterns.

Figure 1:

Discussion

Cheiloscopy is an upcoming tool in crime investigation. Though finger prints and DNA comparison are most commonly used, additional tools like cheiloscopy and palatoscopy can be used for identification.

The commonest lip pattern found in present study was type-1. Various studies carried out in India, done by Sivapathasundaram et al [2], Govindkar [9], and Saraswathi [8], showed type-III as predominant type. Studies of Sharma et al and Verghese et al showed type-IV as predominant type.

The present study coincides with Vahanwalla and Parekh [6] study done in a Mumbai population. This variation in prevalence can be explained by the ethnic and racial differences. Cheiloscopy can be useful for forensic investigation based on available literature irrespective of ethnic origins of a person.

However further studies on lip prints involving a larger cohort study may be useful which can show ethnic, geographic and racial differences if any.

Conclusion

In the present study, lip prints of our study participants did not match with each other. Therefore, the result of our study validates that lip prints are unique as that of finger prints and therefore has forensic importance. Regional population variation in prevalence pattern merits further study, and hence in future could gain more anthropological significance.

Even though there is no significant difference in lip patterns of males and females, studies with larger

sample may be used for depicting sex differentiation if any and its use in identification.

References

1. Rajendran R, Sivapathasundharam B. Shafer's Textbook of Oral Pathology. Sixth. New Delhi, India: Elsevier; 2006. pp. 896–897.
2. Sivapathasundharam B, Prakash PA, Sivakumar G. Lip prints (Cheiloscopy) Indian J Dent Res. 2001;12:234–7.
3. Verghese AJ, Shashidhar C, Mestri A Study of Efficacy of Lip Prints as an Identification Tool among the People of Karnataka in India. J Indian Acad Forensic Med. 2011 Jul-Sep; 33:200–202.
4. Kasprzak J. Possibilities of cheiloscopy. Forensic Sci Int. 1990; 46:145–151.
5. Thomas CJ, van Wyk CW. The palatal rugae in identification. J Forensic Odontostomatol. 1988; 6:21–7.
6. Tsuchihashi Y. Studies on personal identification by means of lip prints. Forensic Sci. 1974; 3:233–248.
7. Vahanwalla SP, Parekh BK. Study on lip prints as an aid to forensic methodology. J Indian Dent Assoc. 2000; 71:268–271.
8. Saraswathi TR, Gauri M, Ranganathan K. Study of lip prints. Journal of Forensic Dental Sciences. 2009; 1:28–31.
9. Gondivkar SM, Indurkar A, Degwekar S, Bhowate R. Cheiloscopy for sex determination. J Forensic Dent Sci. 2009; 1:56–60.
10. MedCalc Statistical Software version 13.0. MedCalc Software bvba; Ostend, Belgium: 2014.